

METASTAVA

METASTAVAHorizon 2020 FAIR DMPv1

Admin details

Project Name METASTAVA

Project Identifier OHEJP-JRP8

Grant Title Standardisation and validation of metagenomics methods for the detection of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

Principal Investigator / Researcher Valerie De Waele and steven.vanborm@sciensano.be <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3464-2306>

Description Novel sequencing technologies have a huge potential for the unbiased characterization of the microbial and viral content of human, animal, and food samples. The potential advantages for human and animal health research are the rapid identification of novel pathogens, the characterization of complete microbial communities, and the tracking of origins, sources and transmission pathways of infections. Here, we focus on the potential development of catch-all diagnostics through sequencing of all RNA and DNA in samples, so called metagenomic sequencing. Metagenomic analysis is increasingly used to identify possible causes of unexplained disease outbreaks, to complement routine diagnostic evaluation, and to study the role of the microbiome and virome in health and disease. However, translating these promising technological developments into diagnostic tools for veterinary and public health laboratories requires careful validation, which is the focus of the current proposal. METASTAVA aims to evaluate the potential use of metagenomic analysis to the public health reference laboratory by targeted collection of reference data and reference materials (WP1), by generating focused validation data (WP3), and by proposing criteria and tools for a robust quality assurance (QA) of metagenomic workflows from sample selection to interpretation of result (WP2). The proposal will use hepatitis E virus (HEV), norovirus (NoV), zoonotic pox viruses, antibiotic resistant bacteria and Shigatoxigenic Escherichia coli (STEC), also known as verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) as model pathogens in developing the methods and reference datasets. We will address the following key objectives: (1) Develop a set of reference data for the model pathogens, representing most common sample types, (2) Develop harmonized workflows for the generation and analysis of metagenomic data fitting to a defined diagnostic scope for the model pathogens, (3) Develop a validation protocol for metagenomic diagnostics (including quality assurance and robustness testing). In short, where ongoing initiatives invest in the standardization of metagenomics tool sets, METASTAVA wants to bring metagenomics to the diagnostic laboratory.

Funder European Commission (Horizon 2020)

Version information

Version number

v2.0

Description

update jan 2020

Date of first version

26/03/2019

Date of last update

13/01/2020

1. Data summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- Collecting validation data to understand and document the analytical test properties (sensitivity, specificity, robustness) of metagenomic workflows for model pathogens (in their most relevant sample matrices), including hepatitis E virus (HEV), norovirus, zoonotic pox viruses, antibiotic resistant bacteria and Shigatoxigenic Escherichia coli (STEC).
- Collecting reference data to allow informed design of metagenomics experiments fitting to a precisely defined diagnostic question
- Identifying knowledge and data gaps in consultation with ongoing initiatives (COMPARE, EFFORT, GMI, and ISO workgroups).
- Proposing quality assurance metrics to guide the evaluation and interpretation of metagenomics datasets.
- Provide dissemination of outcome of METASTAVA to the scientific community, stakeholders and policy makers, to promote a correct understanding of the potential diagnostic use of metagenomics tools.
- Ensure interlaboratory reproducibility of metagenomic methods

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

- research data. Genetic data, raw reads. Total project < 1Tb
- research data. Assembled/analysed data e.g. taxonomic profiles, contigs, read counts, alignments
- Documentation. Reports on Analytical properties corresponding to D-jrp8-3.3 - D-jrp8-3.6
- Documentation. Report methodology selection. Text. D-jrp8-1.1 and D-jrp8-1.2. D-jrp8-3.2
- Documentation. Sample selection database. D-jrp8-3.1
- Events (webinars, meetings etc) with other initiatives. D-jrp8-4.1
- Research data + guidelines. Text.
- presentations, publications. Open source dissemination of output.
- Documentation. Report. D-jrp8-2.5
- documentation. Periodic and continuous reporting.

Will you re-use any existing data and, if so, how?

Public sequence databases will be used for comparison (NCBI nt, nr, ...)

What is the origin of the data?

- New data generated for the project
- derived data from above new data

What is the expected size of the data (if known)?

Question not answered.

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?

Depending on the data type: metastava consortium, OHEJP consortium, scientific community, national authorities, supranatural bodies.

2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?

1. Because of the co-funding setup of OH-EJP, with Programme Managers receiving their mandate from Programme Owners, agreements have to be made between OH-EJP partners and relevant data national owners/providers to ensure data discoverability and identifiability. During the course of the program, the relevance and opportunity to make those co-funded data findable and accessible to other OH-EJP partners will be assessed case by case. Different considerations will be taken into account to support the decision of making those data findable, such as scientific relevance of data for other OH-EJP partners, technical feasibility, formal agreement with the data owners/providers, and compliance with national and EU ethic-legal framework. 2. The assignment and management of persistent identifiers to the data will be assessed in the course of the project. Most repositories are providing automatically persistent identifiers such as DOI, e.g. the functionality provided by Zenodo platform.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism?

It is expected that the OH-EJP integrative projects will develop relevant metadata frameworks in the course of their project based on existing standards and/or frameworks. Discipline-specific metadata standards are dictated by the used genomic and sequence read databases.

What naming conventions do you follow?

For deliverables: "D Name of deliverables". For other data generated by OH-EJP Consortium, the recommended naming convention consisting in 3 mandatory parts separated by an underscore: •A prefix with a short and meaningful name of data; •A root composed by: the acronym of the project and he acronym of the project "OHEJP"; •A suffix indicating the date of the last upload into the repository in YYYYMMDD format.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

To facilitate the queries by keywords, metadata elements need to be

aligned across the OH-EJP. Therefore, the metadata elements must include the term “OHEJP”, to facilitate finding of OH-EJP data. Discipline-specific metadata standards are dictated by the used genomic and sequence read databases and optimize possibilities for re-use.

What is your approach for clear versioning?

Question not answered.

What metadata will be created?

- sample related metadata
- laboratory workflow related metadata
- bioinformatic analysis related metadata

2.2. FAIR data: Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If some data is kept closed provide a rationale for doing so.

Open access will be the default for all relevant data types (raw data, genomes, research data, publications, etc.). However, we have to differentiate between samples originating from humans vs. animals or food matrices. **human samples:** Open access is incompatible with rules on protecting personal data: protection of the personal right needs to be ascertained either by avoiding open access to sensitive and personal data, or by anonymizing the data if relevant and feasible. The presence of human genomic sequences in these datasets cannot be ruled out. **animal samples:** Open access of raw data and publications. relevance of access to intermediate analysis results will be investigated during the course of the project.

How will the data be made accessible?

- Sequence information (raw or derived): deposition in public sequence databases
- Deliverables will be made findable and accessible through the OH-EJP platform. Some deliverables will be kept confidential, but most will be made publicly available. Public deliverables will be linked to the open repository where they were deposited in machine-readable format. Example of repository: the OHEJP community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/ohejp?page=1&size=20>
- open access publication will be required (gold/full open access or green open access.)

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

specialised tools and languages, standard to the field.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation, and code be deposited? Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Question not answered.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

Question not answered.

2.3. FAIR data: Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable? What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

- all produced genetic data follow standard genomic data formats (fastq, fasta, etc.)
- text output (reports, publications) follow standard formats.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

There is a lack of metadata standards for the One-Health surveillance domain. A common vocabulary, codes list and mapping of pre-defined values for harmonising the descriptions of metadata and data will be defined in the course of the integrative projects. The consortium will reuse existing controlled vocabularies for providing metadata to resources as far as possible. Controlled vocabularies for reused can be found on Joinup (<http://joinup.ec.europa.eu>) and Linked Open Vocabularies (<http://lov.okfn.org>) platforms. If there is no suitable authoritative reusable vocabulary for describing data, conventions will be used for describing the vocabulary: RDF Schema (RDFS) and/or Web Ontology Language (OWL). The best practice when new terms are required, is to define their range and domain.

2.4. FAIR data: Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Question not answered.

When will the data be made available for re-use? If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.

The specific decision on an embargo for research data will be taken by the responsible OH-EJP partners. Scientific research articles should have an open access at the latest on publication if in an Open Access journal, or within 6 months of publication. For research data, open access should by default be provided when the associated research paper is available in open access.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Public data will be available from open repositories, and therefore reusable by third parties, even after the end of the project. For confidential data, access to personal data will be compliant with GDPR, while data concerning intellectual property will be discussed between relevant partners, and decision will be taken according to the European and national rules.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

A strategy for storage of the files after the project will be included in the DMP in the course of the project. Regarding data stored on the sub-community One-Health EJP on OpenAIRE platform, all files stored within the repository shall be stored after the project to meet the requirements of good scientific practice. For data stored on other repositories, researchers, institutions, journals and data repositories have a shared responsibility to ensure long-term data preservation. Partners must commit to preserving their datasets, on their own institutional servers, for at least five years after publication. If, during that time, the repository to which the data were originally submitted disappears or experiences data loss, the partners will be required to upload the data to another repository and publish a correction or update to the original persistent identifier if required.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Firstly, some partner institute have existing data quality assurance processes, which can be described in their quality manual. Secondly, publications will be disseminated using peer-reviewed journals, and similarly, research data will be deposited on repositories providing curation system appropriate to the data. The development of a curation system for the sub-community One-Health EJP on OpenAIRE platform will be discussed by the PTM.

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these costs be covered?

Costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

For JRP-8-METASTAVA, the project lead (Steven Van Borm) and deputy lead (Dirk Höper) share responsibility for the general data management principles. Partners have individual responsibility for the data they generate and make publicly available.

What are the costs and potential value of long term preservation?

Question not answered.

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

All participants follow their institutional data security procedures.

Data protection officer contacts:

- Sciensano InformationSecurity@sciensano.be
- FLI datenschutz@fli.de
- ANSES data protection officer : Director of Legal Affairs (saisine-daj@anses.fr)
- SVA registrator@sva.se
- WBVR functionarisgegevensbescherming@wur.nl.
- EMC functionaris.gegevensbescherming@erasmusmc.nl

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Ethical aspects are largely covered in the context of the ethics review, the ethics section of the Description of the Action and the ethics deliverables. The storage and transfer of data on human subjects to the repositories used by the consortium are only considered in case of informed consents, ethics approval, compliance with GDPR and – when applicable - approval by local data protection authorities. Partners are expected to describe in detail any controls or limitations on access to or usage of human data in the ethic section of the Project DMP. The process by which researchers may apply for access to the data, and the conditions under which such access may be granted, should similarly be described. Partners will follow recommendations received from the ethics advisors, as described in the Description of the Action.

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

Question not answered.